

Acute Lower Limb Ischemia during Covid 19 Infection, a Worrying Complication!

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Publication Online: 30 July 2021	Admittedly, the respiratory picture remains the most classic, however, covid 19 is lately considered to be a vasculitis affecting several organs, and therefore which is the origin of other extra-pulmonary manifestations, in particular thromboembolic disease (both venous and arterial) which has increasingly become a dramatic complication to be feared during this pandemic, due to its negative impact on the prognosis of affected patients, increasing the need for a resuscitation environment and the death rate. The mechanism is multifactorial, associating endothelial damage, an abnormality of hemostasis, and immunothrombosis [1]. We report the case of a 52-year-old young patient who had an acute ischemia of his left lower limb, by embolization of a thrombus located in the left ventricle, during his involvement by covid 19 and who was taken in charge immediately. The interest of this observation is to shed light on this complication which often accompanies infection by covid 19, which has become, not only a respiratory disease, but also a vasculitis with its significant risk of thromboembolism.
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INTRODUCTION

Covid 19 disease is currently a health problem internationally, given its power to spread exponentially, causing not only health but also socioeconomic repercussions. Its clinical presentation can range from an asymptomatic profile to a serious clinical form including acute respiratory distress syndrome, or death. In addition to these fairly frequent complications, thromboembolic damage has been described. Recent evidence in Wuhan has shown that 3% of patients admitted for CoVid-19 infection subsequently presented with cardiac thrombosis, with peripheral embolic complication in 0.5% [2], which allowed to focus on the interest of curative anticoagulation in covid disease 19.

CASE REPORT

This is a 52-year-old patient, with no medical history or known thromboembolic risk factors, who presented to the emergency room for a dry cough in a febrile background complicated by NYHA stage III then IV dyspnea. On clinical examination, we find Glasgow score at 15, polyyps, blood pressure normal, HR at 95 b / min, SpO2 at 90%. The cardiac

examination is unremarkable, and there is a crepitating sensation on pulmonary auscultation.

The EKG shows a regular sinus rhythm, incomplete right bundle branch block.

Considering the context of the pandemic, with the symptomatology of the patient, a PCR of SARS-COV-2 was performed returning positive, and a thoracic CT revealed an aspect in favor of a Covid 19 corads 5 infection (Figure 1).

A first transthoracic echocardiography (TTE) was performed showing cardiac chambers of normal size with a normal ejection fraction without leakage or valvular stenosis, or presence of thrombus.

The patient was put on conventional treatment for Covid 19, with curative HBPM-based anticoagulation and simple anti-platelet aggregation.

The evolution was marked by the installation on the 7th day of hospitalization, of acute pain in the left lower limb, with clinical examination of clinical signs of ischemia of the limb, in particular coldness in relation to the limb. Contralateral, and decrease or even abolition of the pulses, with hypoesthesia.

A control TTE was performed urgently, revealing a very mobile and floating left intraventricular thrombus, including

the base of insertion and very thin, barely visible, at the level of the septum, measuring 26x11mm (Figure 2).

A vascular echodoppler was performed, revealing a left popliteal thrombus. The patient was taken immediately to the operating room for urgent action. With a favorable evolution with the setting under a good curative intravenous anticoagulation, with echocardiographic monitoring close to the thrombus which seems to decrease in size.

DISCUSSION

Despite its respiratory tropism, covid 19 disease, the rate of thromboembolic events remains significant [3].

Numerous studies have made it possible to advance the understanding of the mechanisms, prevention and treatment of thromboembolic events (TEE) associated with COVID-19, finally concluding that there are three main mechanisms:

First, a disease of the endothelium [4] which constitutes an interface between the blood and the tissues and whose role is to maintain vascular homeostasis through its anti-aggregating and anticoagulant properties. After SARS-CoV-2 enters the airways, damage to alveolar epithelial cells and pulmonary endothelial cells will occur and cause a local inflammatory storm spreading to endothelial cells and causing generalized endothelitis.

A hypothesis of immunothrombosis [5] is suggested in the mechanism of thromboembolic events during covid 19, and which is of particular interest to platelets. These normally play the role of a key mediator of the relationship between inflammation and coagulation. During covid 19 infection, SARS Cov2 causes platelet hyperreactivity thus increasing thrombotic phenomena.

Finally, like any viral infection, sepsis secondary to COVID-19 causes the release of pro-inflammatory cytokines, thus causing a cytokine storm responsible for an imbalance between procoagulant and fibrinolytic factors leading to the formation of thromboses. Hypoxia also intervenes by its effect stimulating the synthesis of procoagulant factors which can go in severe forms up to disseminated intravascular coagulation [6].

Because covid 19 is an inflammatory disease affecting the arteries and veins, the accumulation of inflammatory cells can be observed in the endothelium of different organs [7].

Indeed, of the 150 patients included in this study, 64 presented with such complications, mainly pulmonary embolism in 25 patients (ie in more than 16% of cases). Half of the cases were diagnosed with pulmonary embolism 5 days after admission to intensive care. Mesenteric ischemia was suspected in 5 patients (ie 3% of cases). Other patients developed a stroke [8].

In an article in the journal Intensive Care Medicine, a study was conducted in China [9] reporting a high risk of life-threatening thromboembolic complications in Covid-19 patients with acute respiratory distress syndrome. These

thromboembolic complications set in despite the initiation of preventive or therapeutic anticoagulant treatment.

In addition, 28 of the 29 patients on dialysis for kidney failure developed a clot that blocked the hemodialysis circuit.

All the major series mention the occurrence of ischemia of the lower limbs [10], at a frequency ranging from 1% [11] to 3.5% [12].

Intracardiac thrombosis may set in within a median of 5 days after onset of the first symptoms of COVID 19 [13,14], as it may initiate the clinical picture before the onset of respiratory signs in rare cases.

A study conducted in China in 2020, for patients with CoVid-19 infection, 0.5% of patients presented ischemia of the lower limbs by thrombus embolization, despite good preventive anticoagulation.

The diagnostic means in case of ischemia of the lower limbs with COVID 19 remain the same, in particular: a Doppler of the lower limbs should be performed urgently which has a sensitivity of 85% [15]. It can be coupled with the performance of an angio-CT of the lower limbs which allows visualization of the entire vascular bed of the limbs and to locate the embolus or the thrombus, with the downstream bed. Arteriography, in emergency, it constitutes the reference examination. It precisely determines the location of the attack with its impact on the downstream bed, it shows in the event of embolism a sudden stop in the cup without collateral circulation, and in the event of thrombosis an irregular stop with staged lesions and the presence of collateral circulation, and it also allows therapeutic action.

Further check-ups for the etiology are necessary, in particular an EKG for an arrhythmia, transthoracic echocardiography for an intracavitary thrombus such as the case of our patient, ultrasound of the supra-aortic trunks (to look for another localization of embolization), inflammatory workup, specialized hemostasis workup, d-dimers, fibrinogen, NFS, platelets, TP, TCA, antithrombin III, protein C, protein S).

Therapeutically, medical treatment based on curative anticoagulation with unfractionated heparin is always indicated.

Then a surgical or endovascular treatment is discussed according to the stage of ischemia (classification of Rutherford), general and cardiovascular state, the state of the vascular bed and downstream bed, the thrombotic or embolic origin and the level of 'occlusion.

For Stages I and II in case of embolism is on a healthy artery: if it is proximal an embolectomy by Fogarty catheter or an in situ thrombolysis is recommended, and if it is distal thrombosuction is preferred. While in case of embolism on an atheromatous artery, we recommend an in situ thrombolysis associated with an angioplasty or plasty depending on the downstream bed and the length of the lesion

Finally, unfortunately in the event of a Stage III attack, an amputation remains the only course of action to take.

A Chinese study published in the Journal of Thrombosis and Haemostasis [16], reports that abnormal results of biological markers of coagulation, in particular high levels of D-dimer and fibrin degradation products, are associated with a poor prognosis in Covid-19 patients with pneumonia with a thromboembolic event. [17].

CONCLUSION

Being an inflammatory viral disease, COVID 19 is accompanied by venous thromboembolic complications, but also arterial and microvascular complications which are becoming more and more significant, putting the patient's vital prognosis at risk.

Intracardiac thrombosis and peripheral embolization constitute 1%, hence the need for additional research to better elucidate the pathophysiological mechanisms as well as the diagnostic and therapeutic peculiarities of these patients in order to properly control their management, and therefore to minimize the rate of amputation, and transfer to intensive care.

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FIGURE LEGENDS

Figure 1: Thoracic TM showing an aspect in favor of covid 19 infection involving 70% of the lung parenchyma.

Figure 2: echocardiographic image 9 parasternal small axis transVG and 4 cavities) showing an intracavitary thrombus (left ventricle)

Figure 1

Figure 2